

Late Variscan Tectonic Orogenic Collapse as a Trigger of Sn-W Mineralizing Systems. U-Pb ore Geochronology Across the Martinamor Gneissic Dome (Salamanca, Spain).

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Key Words: U-Pb geochronology cassiterite and wolframite; Gneissic dome; Extensional detachment; Central Iberian Zone; Variscan gravitational collapse; Central Iberian Arc orocline; Heat advection, Iberian Massif

Abstract

Tectonothermal evolution is a primary factor on many mineral deposits. Late orogenic gravitational collapse has been widely recognized across different orogens, including the Variscan belt. The Martinamor gneissic dome is a well constrained structure related to the Late-Variscan orogenic collapse in the Iberian Massif. We have investigated Sn-W mineralizations spatially related to the Martinamor dome by LA-ICP-MS U-Pb dating of cassiterite and wolframite, revealing a wide mineralization timespan of 40 Myr. Our results show: a) an early (338.1 ± 5.8 Ma), minor mineralization phase, (W-dominated), potentially related to variscan compressive phases; b) a second, major stage which lasted from 324.1 ± 5.9 to 300.7 ± 5.4 Ma, which includes Sn-bearing pegmatites and Sn-W veins formed under the syncollisional extensional collapse. Structural evidence highlights the role of extensional detachments in channeling mineralizing fluids and creating suitable traps under ductile and ductile-brittle conditions and it also explains the temporal and spatial distribution of the Sn-W vein-type mineralizations in the zone.

Comparisons with other Variscan deposits in the Iberian Massif and European counterparts suggest a regional metallogenic cycle linked to late-Variscan extensional collapse, heat advection, and partial melting processes. These findings underscore the Martinamor dome as a unique structure recording a major Variscan tectono-magmatic-metallogenic event, with implications for understanding Sn-W deposit formation in orogenic contexts.

1. Introduction

The European Variscan orogen is a major metallogenic Sn-W belt comprising four main provinces, i.e., Cornwall, the Bohemian Massif, the Iberian Massif, and the French Massif Central. Different styles of

36 magmatic-hydrothermal Sn-W mineralization, including disseminated cassiterite in greisenized granites,
37 cassiterite-bearing pegmatites, cassiterite-quartz veins and lodes, wolframite-quartz veins, scheelite skarns
38 and stratabound skarnoids, occur mostly hosted by, or spatially associated with, peraluminous S-type
39 granitic intrusions. Emplacement of these fertile, crustal-derived magmas took place over a period of ca.
40 50 Ma, between 330 and 280 Ma (Marignac and Cuney, 1999; Breiter et al., 1999; Cuney et al., 2002;
41 Villaseca, 2011; Chicharro et al., 2014; Harlaux et al., 2018; Roda-Robles et al., 2018; among others), in a
42 late collisional to post-collisional tectonic setting. The extensional collapse of the orogen was diachronous
43 at the scale of the Variscan belt (Burg et al., 1994), thus resulting in the co-existence of contrasting tectonic
44 regimes in which different Sn-W metallogenic episodes took place (e.g. Cuney et al., 2002; Bouchot et al.,
45 2005; Harlaux et al., 2018).

46 In the Iberian Massif (Spain and Portugal), Sn-W deposits are mostly related to two different S-type
47 peraluminous granitoid suites (Antona et al., 1994; Dias et al., 1998; Llorens and Moro, 2012a and 2012b;
48 Chicharro et al., 2014; 2016, Timón-Sánchez et al., 2019; Losada et al., 2022; Borrajo et al., 2024). The S1
49 suite mainly consists of syn-orogenic two-mica leucogranites emplaced around 330-311 Ma (Texeira et al.,
50 2012; López-Moro et al., 2012; Roda-Robles et al., 2018), whereas the S2 suite comprise P-rich
51 monzogranites intruded between 314 and 296 Ma (Gutierrez-Alonso et al., 2011; Chicharro et al., 2014;
52 Merino-Martínez et al., 2014; Roda-Robles et al., 2018). Only a small group of W-rich deposits are related
53 to I-type metaluminous to low peraluminous granitoids (Borrajo et al., 2024), mainly emplaced between
54 303 to 280 Ma (Dias et al., 1998; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2000; Villaseca et al., 2009; Gutiérrez-Alonso et
55 al., 2011; Orejana et al., 2012). The S2 and I granitoids were likely associated with the post-orogenic
56 lithospheric thinning and mantle input around 310-300 Ma (Gutierrez-Alonso et al., 2011).
57 Geochronological data from ore minerals (i.e., U-Pb in cassiterite, columbite-tantalite and rutile, Melleton
58 and Gloaguen, 2015; Zhang et al., 2019; Carocci et al., 2020; Melleton et al., 2022; and Re-Os in
59 molybdenite, Moura et al., 2014; Borrajo et al., 2024) evidence Sn-W metallogenic activity from ca. 340 to
60 278 Ma at the Iberian province scale, allowing to connect ore-forming episodes with specific intrusions
61 within this time frame.

62 In this work we have selected a well-known brown-field Sn-W district in the southern domain of the Central
63 Iberian Zone (CIZ; Iberian Massif): The Morille-Martinamor mining district (Spain) with many small Sn-
64 W deposits intermittent mined in the 20th century (Pellitero, 1981a, 1981b; Gonzalo and Gracia-Plaza,
65 1985; Barrios et al., 2020). This district is a singular case departing in different aspects from the general

66 framework depicted above. The Sn-W mineralization, consisting of cassiterite±wolframite±scheelite-
67 bearing quartz veins with a variety of structural styles, and scheelite stratabound skarnoids, mostly occur
68 hosted by metasedimentary rocks within an extensional shear zone more than 4 km thick (the Salamanca
69 Detachment Zone, Díez Balda et al., 1995) in the Martinamor dome. In this context, the structural features
70 of the mineralized veins are key to establishing their relative chronology (Bermejo et al., 2023).
71 The majority of previous investigations in this area have either been focused on site/deposit-scale analysis
72 or has not been aware of the existence of the extensional shear zone, resulting in a limited district- to
73 regional-scale correlation (e.g. Tornos et al., 2008; Barrios et al., 2020; García Sánchez and Gracia Plaza,
74 1981; Jiménez Benayas et al., 1996; Timón Sánchez et al., 2018).

75

76 The aim of this paper is to uncover the spatio-temporal distribution of the Morille-Martinamor Sn-W
77 deposits and recognize the links between these deposits and the broader regional geodynamics. To this end,
78 we have integrated structural, geochronological and metallogenetic information to constrain the regional
79 meaning of these Sn-W deposits and shed some light on the Variscan tin-belt in Iberia. Direct dating of ore
80 minerals (i.e. U-Pb in cassiterite and wolframite) combined with their trace element geochemistry have
81 been completed for the first time in this district, providing new data to discuss the role of the late orogenic
82 tectonics and the formation of Sn-W deposits in this sector of the Iberian Massif.

83

84 **2. Geological setting**

85 **2.1. The Iberian Massif**

86 The Variscan Orogen resulted from the collision of Laurussia and Gondwana during the assembly of the
87 Pangea supercontinent in the Paleozoic (Ballèvre et al., 2014; Quesada and Oliveira 2019; Martínez Catalán
88 et al., 2020, 2021). The Iberian Massif represents the largest outcrop of the Variscan basement in Iberia and
89 it is divided into six zones (Farias et al., 1987) (Fig. 1). The Cantabrian (CZ), West Asturian-Leonese
90 (WALZ), Central Iberian (CIZ), Ossa-Morena (OMZ), and South Portuguese (SPZ) zones represent the
91 autochthon domain while the Galicia-Tras Os Montes zone (GTMZ) includes, a parautochthonous thrust
92 sheet, and an allochthonous nappe stack. The Autochthon is formed by metasediments, metavolcanics and
93 orthogneisses respectively deposited, extruded and intruded during the Neoproterozoic and Paleozoic in the
94 northern Gondwana margin, as indicated by sedimentary and faunal evidence and by detrital zircon age
95 populations (Robardet, 2003; Martínez Catalán et al., 2004; Gutiérrez Alonso et al., 2015; Martínez Catalán

96 et al., 2016; Azor et al., 2019). The Parautochthon consists of Cambrian, Ordovician, and Silurian
97 metasediments and volcanics exhibiting stratigraphic and igneous affinities with the Autochthon, and
98 representing a distal part of the Gondwanan continental margin (Farias et al., 1987; Dias da Silva et al.,
99 2014). Deformation and metamorphism are related to the Variscan orogeny, and early Carboniferous
100 synorogenic flysch type deposits related with the emplacement of the allochthonous complexes occur in
101 both the Autochthon and Parautochthon, (Martínez Catalán et al., 2008; 2016; Dias da Silva et al., 2014;
102 González Clavijo et al., 2020).

103 A regional structural evolution is recognized across the Iberian Massif, including contractional (C) and
104 extensional (E) deformation phases (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014). The first contractional phase (C1) had
105 different structural expressions across the CIZ, with regional scale eastward vergence recumbent folds in
106 the northern and subvertical folds in the southern domain (Díez Balda et al., 1990). The second contractional
107 phase (C2) is characterized by tangential deformation, with major thrusts, followed by the third
108 contractional phase (C3) which formed vertical folds and late strike-slip tectonics (Azor et al., 2019). As a
109 result of the crustal thickening during C1 and C2, an early extensional collapse occurred (E1), with the
110 development of gneissic domes. Persistent convergence and thickening during C3 and large-scale orocline
111 formation activated a second phase of extensional collapse (E2) (Martínez Catalán et al., 2018; Durán Oreja
112 et al., 2023).

113 Gneiss domes hosting late Variscan migmatites and a diverse array of granitoids are prevalent in the
114 Galicia-Tras Os Montes Zone (Fig.1; e.g. Celanova dome, Alcock et al., 2015; Rubio Pascual et al., 2022;
115 Padrón dome, Díez Fernandez et al., 2012; Alcock et al., 2015) and in the Central Iberian Zone (Fig. 2; e.g.
116 Tormes dome, Viruete et al., 1994; Martinamor-Castellanos dome, Díez Balda et al., 1995). They partly
117 originated from the partial melting of high-grade paragneisses and were subsequently intruded by younger
118 late Variscan leucogranites (310-285 Ma; Martínez Catalán et al., 2014). These characteristics indicate that
119 gneiss domes formed due to region-scale crustal flow with an associated synkinematic low-pressure
120 metamorphism, which extends into the core of the gneissic dome reaching partial melting conditions (Block
121 and Royden, 1990; Thompson and McCarthy, 1990; Whitney et al., 2013). This synkinematic low-pressure
122 metamorphism overprints Barrovian prograde metamorphism caused by the crustal thickening during
123 previous compressional events.

124 While a spatial correlation exists between late Variscan tectonic, gneiss dome development and extensive
125 synkinematic granitic magmatism in the Iberian Massif (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014), little is known about

126 the link between Sn-W ore deposits and the multiphase tectonothermal evolution of the orogen (e.g.
127 Bouchot et al., 2005; Harlaux et al., 2021).

128

129 2.2 The geology of the Martinamor gneissic dome

130 Our investigation focuses on the Martinamor gneissic dome, located on the central area of the CIZ (Fig. 1),
131 about 15 km south of Salamanca city, Spain. This is a westward-dipping dome capped by a broad shear
132 zone with more than 4 km thick (Martínez-Catalán et al. 2019). The outcropping lithological units in this
133 structure comprise a sequence of pre-Ordovician metasedimentary rocks (Monterrubio and Aldeatejada
134 formations, belonging to the Schist-Greywacke Complex, late Proterozoic-early Cambrian); granitic rocks,
135 and Tertiary sedimentary rocks (Fig. 2). The granitic rocks mostly crop out in the eastern part of the dome,
136 within the Monterrubio formation, and include 1) the pre-Variscan San Pelayo Orthogneiss, 2) the
137 Martinamor Granitic Complex, a swarm of lenticular leucogranitic and pegmatite bodies, which are
138 subconcordant to the host rock foliation and exhibit a planoliner and horizontal fabric (Díez Balda et al.
139 1995), and 3) the Santa Genoveva granitic stock (U-Pb zircon age of 298 ± 28 Ma, Galibert, 1984), which
140 intruded the Monterrubio metasediments.

141 In the investigated area, Variscan compressional phases include an early C1 phase which led to NNW-SSE
142 subvertical folds, locally identified to the SW of the Martinamor dome. There is no evidence of C2
143 structures, typically represented by subhorizontal shear zones and thrust-faults in other sectors of the Iberian
144 Massif (Díez Balda et al., 1995; Azor et al., 2019). The C3 phase is well developed, with NW-SE to WNW-
145 ESE vertical folds, and the development of a penetrative tectonic foliation (S3). This phase has overwritten
146 most of C1 structural signature in the area. Contractional phases led to Barrovian metamorphism (peak
147 conditions at 5.5kbar and $>650^\circ\text{C}$; Díez Balda et al., 1995). In this sector of the orogen, both, contractional
148 structures and Barrovian isogrades, were later overwritten by extensional structures associated with
149 syncollisional gravitational collapse of the orogen (Díez Balda et al. 1995, Martínez Catalán et al., 2014;
150 Vanderhaeghe et al., 2020). In the area, extensional deformation post-date C3 vertical folds, belonging to
151 the second extensional phase (E2 variscan phase; Azor et al., 2019). It has been accommodated by an
152 extensional detachment (Fig. 2), with the development of a penetrative subhorizontal foliation (S_{E2}) and a
153 general top-to-the SE sense of shear, which transposed and completely obliterated previous foliations (i.e.
154 S3; Díez Balda et al., 1995). Episodes of partial melting synkinematic with E2 phase are documented across
155 the lowermost structural levels of the detachment, which crop out in the SE area of the Martinamor dome

156 (Díez Balda et al., 1995). The final geometry of the dome was the result of an upward flow to compensate
157 lateral extensional spreading in the hanging-wall to the detachment. Alpine reactivation of NNE-SSW
158 trending Variscan faults eventually defined a horst-and-graben geometry which explain the abrupt transition
159 of basement lithologies into late Cenozoic deposits (Fig. 2).

160 The extensional detachment (E2) led to a tectonic condensation of the original pile and put into contact
161 relatively shallow structural levels with deeper sections (e.g. Gómez Barreiro et al. 2010; Álvarez Valero
162 et al., 2014; Martínez Catalán et al. 2003; Foster et al. 2023). In the field, the upper limit of the extensional
163 strain gradient is the garnet isograd (Fig. 2). In the hanging-wall to the detachment, metasediments of the
164 Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC) appear only affected by compressional phases (C1 and C3) under
165 greenschists facies conditions (chlorite/biotite zone, Díez Balda et al. 1995). In the footwall to the
166 detachment, SGC metasediments have reached amphibolite facies conditions during compressional phases
167 (Staurolite/Sillimanite zone, Díez Balda et al. 1995), however mineral assemblages and structures appear
168 overprinted by E2 extensional ones. In the dome core laminar syn-kynematic two-mica granitoids are
169 widespread, being subconcordant to the host rock foliation (S_{E2}) and exhibiting a planoliner mylonitic
170 fabric. In addition, several outcrops of Ordovician orthogneisses are found (Fig. 2; Díez Balda et al. 1995).

171 In the footwall to the detachment, Barrovian mineral assemblages are substituted by low-P assemblages,
172 mainly andalusite, pointing to an isothermal exhumation of the footwall rocks from about 5 kbar to 2 kbar
173 (Díez Balda et al. 1995). Deformation conditions across the extensional detachment are consistent with
174 those findings and show a consistent top-to-the SE sense of shear (Díez Balda et al., 1995; Gómez Barreiro
175 et al., 2024).

176 There is a widespread Sn-W mineralization across the extensional shear zone gradient and downward into
177 the footwall. Three main mineralization types occur in this zone; i) Sn-bearing pegmatites and ii)
178 stratabound W mineralization in calc-silicate levels, especially at the shallowest structural levels, and iii)
179 Sn-W vein-type mineralization across all the dome. The presence of vein-type Sn-W mineralization at
180 different structural levels across the Martinamor gneissic dome represents an excellent opportunity to
181 constrain the timing and evolution of the hydrothermal activity within the tectonothermal evolution of this
182 sector of the Iberian Massif. A detailed study of the structural sequence of the Sn-W Morille-Martinamor
183 deposits area can be found in Díez Balda et al. (1995) and Bermejo et al. (2023). Within the Martinamor
184 gneiss dome, distinct mineralized tensional structures have been identified connected to Sn-W
185 mineralization, most of them coeval with extensional phase. However, in the uppermost part of the

186 extensional shear zone, we cannot completely rule out the imprint of the partially coeval compressional
187 stresses (C3) in the formation of some deposits. In this complex context, geochronology is bound to play
188 an important role in deciphering the connection between mineralizing pulses and structures, and particularly
189 the extension of the mineralization processes in relation to tectonothermal evolution both local and regional
190 across the NW Iberian Massif. This is the main objective of our contribution.

191

192 **3. Samples and methods**

193 We selected six representative Sn-W mines across the Martinamor dome to study the vein-type
194 mineralizations at different structural levels to the extensional detachment shear zone. The field
195 relationships, explained hereinafter in the text, allowed us to define a variety of mineralized vein styles
196 according to their structural position in the gneiss dome, mineralogy, alteration, and deformation style. The
197 selected mines are, from shallower to deeper structural zones: El Cubito (CUB), Mimosa (MIM), La
198 Rescatada (RES), Valle Largo (VAL), Atalaya (ATL), and Matamala (MAT) (Fig. 2)

199 After the sampling, a total of 29 cassiterite and 14 wolframite rock chips were prepared at the Facultad de
200 Ciencias Geológicas of the Universidad Complutense (Madrid, Spain). These rock chips were embedded
201 in 1-inch epoxy mounts, grounded and polished with diamond solution. Among this cohort, 12 cassiterite
202 mounts from the six mines and 3 representative wolframite mounts from ATL and MAT were selected for
203 further characterization. These samples were carbon-coated for their study with SEM-CL and EPMA at the
204 Centro Nacional de Microscopía Electrónica facilities, located at the Universidad Complutense (Madrid,
205 Spain) and at the Servicios Científico-Técnicos of the Universidad de Oviedo (Asturias, Spain). They were
206 lately repolished for the LA-ICP-SF-MS analytical work that was conducted at the Institute of
207 Geochemistry and Petrology at ETH Zürich, Switzerland.

208 **3.1. Optical microscope and Scanning Electron Microscope-Cathodoluminescence (SEM-CL)**

209 The petrographic study was carried out using a reflected light microscope to describe mineral associations
210 and textures, and also to carefully select the most suitable cassiterite and wolframite crystals for their
211 analytical study. Subsequently, cathodoluminescence images of selected cassiterite samples were taken
212 utilizing a JEOL 6400 JSM Thermo-ionic cathode electron gun equipped with a tungsten filament. These
213 images were acquired operating at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV, with a working distance of 39 mm.

214 **3.2. Electron probe microanalysis (EPMA)**

215 A total of 179 analyses were conducted on cassiterite, and 68 analyses were performed on wolframite,
216 targeting both major and minor elements. These measurements were carried out using wavelength
217 dispersive electron probe microanalyzers (WDS–EPMA), specifically the JEOL JXA 8900 M and the
218 CAMEBAX SX-100 models. The WDS–EPMA was operated with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV and a
219 beam current of 20 nA, utilizing a spot size of 5 μm for spatially accurate analysis. The analytical standards
220 and spectral lines employed for the analyses included: Nb_2O_5 (Nb, $L\alpha$), SnO_2 (cassiterite, $L\alpha$), FeO (Fe,
221 $K\alpha$), Ta_2O_5 (Ta, $L\alpha$), MnO (rhodonite, $K\alpha$), TiO_2 (rutile, $K\alpha$), WO_3 (W, $L\alpha$). These parameters and
222 standards were employed to ensure accurate and reliable analysis of both cassiterite and wolframite
223 samples. The data for analyzed samples is reported in Supplementary Data Table 1.

224 **3.3. Laser ablation-inductively coupled plasma-sector field-mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-SF-MS)**

225 A comprehensive analytical study was conducted involving 499 analyses of cassiterite and 61 analyses of
226 wolframite. This investigation focused on determining U-Pb isotopic compositions along with rare earth
227 element and trace element concentrations. LA-ICP-SF-MS was employed for these measurements, utilizing
228 a RESOLUTION S-155 (ASI/Applied Spectra) 193-nm ArF excimer laser system coupled with an Element
229 XR (Thermo) sector-field ICP-MS. The laser ablation process employed a repetition rate of 5 Hz, with a
230 spot diameter of 43 μm for wolframite and 74 μm for cassiterite analysis. The laser energy density applied
231 to the samples was approximately $2.0 \text{ J}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Prior to analyses the sample surface was ablated with 5 pulses
232 to remove surficial Pb. Ablation was conducted within a dual-volume, fast-washout S-155 ablation cell
233 (Laurin Technic), which was continuously flushed with a carrier gas consisting of approximately 0.25
234 $\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ He, as well as make-up gas comprising about $1 \text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ Ar and $2 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ N_2 . To ensure
235 homogenization of the ablated aerosol, it was passed through a squid device before introduction into the
236 plasma. For optimal performance, the ICP-MS instrument is equipped with a high-capacity ($80 \text{ m}^3\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)
237 interface pump, along with jet sampler and normal H-skimmer cones. This configuration achieved a
238 detection efficiency in the range of 2% (based on U in NIST SRM612 glass) (Guillong et al., 2020) while
239 minimizing oxide production ($^{248}\text{ThO}+^{232}\text{Th} + \leq 0.15\%$) and maintaining a U/Th ratio of ca. 1 (on NIST
240 SRM612 glass).

241 For U-Pb dating, intensities on ^{238}U , ^{235}U , ^{232}Th , ^{208}Pb , ^{207}Pb , ^{206}Pb , ^{204}Pb and ^{202}Hg masses were monitored.
242 Measured Pb-Pb and U-Pb ratios were initially corrected for drift and LIEF using the U-Pb data reduction
243 scheme in Iolite 4 software (Paton et al., 2010, 2011) with NIST SRM 614 glass as the primary reference
244 material. The assumed $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ composition of NIST SRM 614 was 0.8708 ± 0.0002 and $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ was

245 0.70488 ± 0.0070 calculated from published concentration data (Jochum et al., 2011). Drift-corrected and
246 normalized Pb-isotope ratios obtained in Iolite 4 were then exported offline for further data reduction and
247 age calculation. For cassiterite analyses, using the U-Pb age of Yankee cassiterite as reference (Carr et al.,
248 2020) we calculated a correction factor for the $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ ratio for each measurement session, which
249 corresponds to the quotient of the NIST SRM 614-corrected $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ and the $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ calculated from
250 the published U-Pb age. Final ratios were interpreted by the lower intercept method in Tera-Wasserburg
251 diagrams, with $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ vs. $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ lower intercept age calculation and data plotting performed using
252 the IsoplotR toolkit (Vermeesch, 2018). Analysis of cassiterite material with published (RG-114, BB#7,
253 19GX; Yang et al., 2022) and in-house (PAN-2 and BOH-7) isotope dilution-thermal ionization mass
254 spectrometry (ID-TIMS) ages ensures accuracy and reproducibility across analytical sessions. For
255 wolframite analyses, we used a similar offline correction procedure but using the age of wolframite YGX-
256 2113 for reference (Yang et al., 2020) to obtain a session-specific correction factor for the $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ ratio.
257 Analysis of wolframite material with published ID-TIMS and LA-ICP-MS ages (YGX-2107, Sewa; Yang
258 et al., 2020; SHM; Romer and Lüders, 2006) ensures accuracy and reproducibility across analytical
259 sessions. All U-Pb raw and standard-corrected data are reported in Supplementary Data Table 2.
260 Ages and respective uncertainties are reported for both cassiterite and wolframite as $a \pm b$ (c) (Table 2)
261 where a is the lower intercept age in Ma, b is the analytical uncertainty which includes within-session
262 reproducibility and decay constant uncertainty and c is the total uncertainty with excess variance (1.8% for
263 cassiterite; Carr et al., 2023; 2.0% for wolframite; Carr et al., 2021) added in quadrature.
264 For trace element quantification, the intensities obtained in all analyzed masses (complete list in
265 Supplementary Data Table 3) were processed offline with Iolite 4 (Paton et al., 2010, 2011). The USGS
266 GSD-1G (Guillong et al., 2005) glass served as the primary reference material for trace element
267 quantification and instrumental drift correction, utilizing conventional standard-sample bracketing. Internal
268 standards for relative sensitivity corrections were determined based on Fe concentrations obtained via
269 EPMA of both mineral phases. Analytical reproducibility and accuracy were assessed through repeated
270 measurements of the homogeneous NIST SRM610 and SRM614 glass reference materials (Jochum et al.,
271 2011), yielding reproducibility ranges between 10 to 15% (2σ) relative for most elements. The quoted
272 uncertainties for individual analyses encompassed both the internal (2σ) statistical error and analytical
273 reproducibility propagated through quadratic addition. The trace elements data for analyzed samples and
274 validation reference materials are reported in Supplementary Data Table 3.

275

276 **4. Results**

277 **4.1. Structural Control of the Different Mineralization Styles and Related Alteration**

278 Sn and W vein-type deposits in the Martinamor Dome show distinct variations in the styles of mineralized
279 veins and associated mineral assemblages depending on the structural level within the gneissic dome.

280 Wolframite-quartz veins have only been observed in mine tailings of MAT and ATL mines (Table 1),
281 located at the core of the dome, but without structural control on them, and limits how far we could go in
282 interpreting. Conversely, Cassiterite is present throughout the dome with different mineralization styles and
283 mineral associations and a good structural constraint (Fig. 3 & Table 1).

284 To the west of the Martinamor dome shallower structural levels of the shear zone crops-out. There, Sn-
285 bearing quartz veins occur as either individual veins or swarms, predominantly oriented in the NE-SW and
286 E-W directions crosscutting the S3 foliation (e.g. El Cubito mine, CUB), supporting its relation with the
287 NNW-SSE extensional deformation flow. These veins show a greisen-type alteration and tourmalinization,
288 which can significantly transform the surrounding rock as described by García Sánchez and Gracia Plaza
289 (1981). In addition to vein-type deposits, cassiterite-bearing pegmatitic bodies can be found in those levels
290 (e.g. MIM mine) where cassiterite occurs as disseminated crystals. This pegmatite appears deformed,
291 showing boudinage and a rough tectonic fabric, parallel to the external extensional foliation (S_{E2} ; Fig. 3a).

292 Moving east towards the RES and VAL mines, we reach more internal zones of the E2 extensional shear
293 zone. Here, cassiterite-bearing quartz veins are highly deformed. They typically occur as veins associated
294 to boudinage and flanking structures, typically showing a high angle to the extensional flow direction (e.g.
295 Passchier, 2001; Druguet, 2019) suggesting a synkinematic character. Those veins typically occur restricted
296 to high-viscosity layers in the sequence (Boudins necks, Fig. 3b), with minor development in low-viscosity
297 metapelites in which a highly penetrative S_{E2} foliation is identified. In those sections where strain is higher,
298 tensional veins tend to progressively rotate and became parallel to the extensional mylonitic foliation (S_{E2}),
299 with a significant stretching (Fig. 3c). As a result, different generations of veins may overlap, leading to
300 complex geometries, reflecting in all cases the progressive deformation associated with the activity of the
301 extensional detachment. Mineralized veins in those contexts invariably exhibit greisenization selvages and
302 extensive zones of pervasive tourmalinization up to 50 cm thick.

303 In the lowermost structural levels, at ATL and MAT mines, quartz-cassiterite sub-vertical veins dominate,
304 with two predominant orientations of N110-130°E and N30-70°E and fewer signs of progressive

305 deformation reflecting a potential late-kinematic character respect to E2 (Fig. 3d). Interestingly those late
306 veins are associated with greisen-type alteration, without tourmaline.

307

308

309 **4.2. Mineral associations, textures and major elements composition**

310 Wolframite usually occurs as crystal aggregates in quartz and is occasionally associated with scheelite. The
311 wolframite crystals are either centimeter-sized and exhibit tabular morphologies (Fig. 4a) or form
312 millimeter-sized crystal aggregates with no preferred orientation. In this second textural type, wolframite
313 grains can be replaced by a second stage of wolframite characterized by a reddish color (Fig 5b & 5c).

314 The EPMA analyses show that tabular wolframite has 19.3 wt.% MnO and 4.2 wt.% FeO (Hub-1, Table
315 2), whereas composition of millimeter-sized wolframite has an average 14 wt.% of MnO and 9.5 wt.% FeO
316 content (Hub-2, Table 2), both of them corresponding to hubnerite. The wolframite replacing Hub-2 has an
317 average content of 6.3 wt.% MnO and 17.7 wt.% FeO and corresponds to a ferberite term (Fb-2, Table 2).

318 Cassiterite occurs as sub-idiomorphic crystals with a variety of colors and textures in hand specimen, optical
319 microscopy and cathodoluminescence images. The pegmatite-hosted cassiterite (MIM-Cst, Table 1) has a
320 very dark brown color with weak cathodoluminescence response and no observed zoning (Fig. 4d-f).

321 Cassiterites from the vein swarm in the western part of the dome (CUB-Cst-1, CUB-Cst-2, CUB-Cst-3,
322 Table 1) occur as crystals in the center of quartz veins and have significant differences, especially evident
323 in CL images (Fig. 4i). CUB-Cst-1 is characterized by a very dark brown color, highly fractured and
324 dissolved (Fig. 4h) and shows strong CL response with no visible zoning (Fig. 4i). CUB-Cst-2 is usually
325 intergrowth with tourmaline. It is often fractured and dissolved and shows complex zonings with dark
326 brown color intercalated with lighter ones (Fig. 4g). These complex zonings are also shown in CL imaging
327 (Fig. 4i). CUB-Cst-3 is usually related to a variety of sulfides (e.g. arsenopyrite, pyrite, chalcopyrite,
328 stannite and sphalerite). Cassiterite in this sample is neither fractured nor dissolved, shows the lighter color
329 among all the studied cassiterites, and it is characterized by banded growth zoning (Fig. 4i).

330 Cassiterite from sub-horizontal and vertical deformed quartz veins (RES-Cst, VAL-Cst, Table 1) is very
331 similar to the CUB-Cst-2. Grains from these veins often contain abundant tourmaline inclusions and show
332 complex zonings with dark brown color along with lighter zones (Fig. 4j), also visible in CL (Fig. 4i). They

333 are heavily fractured too, displaying many cavities and dissolution-recrystallization zones in which later
334 rutile and columbite have formed (Fig. 4k).

335 Cassiterites from non-deformed, sub-vertical quartz veins (ATL-Cst, MAT-Cst, Table 1) occur as dark
336 brown crystals within quartz veins (Fig. 4m). They show limited fracturing (Fig. 4n) and under CL show
337 banded growth zonings along with petrographic evidence of dissolution and recrystallization in crystal rims
338 and fractures (Fig. 4o), albeit to a far lesser extent than the previously described cassiterites.

339 Average major element composition of cassiterites is >99 wt.% SnO₂ except for CUB-Cst-1, CUB-Cst-3
340 and MIM-Cst cassiterites that have less than 98 wt.% SnO₂ (Table 2). TiO₂ ranges in abundance from 0.05
341 wt.% to 0.88 wt.%, displaying a pattern of progressive depletion from W to E in cassiterites from quartz
342 veins (from W to E respectively, 0.88 → 0.50 → 0.43 → 0.41 → 0.33 → 0.30 wt.% TiO₂) (Table 2). The
343 MIM-Cst and the CUB-Cst-1 cassiterites shows the highest contents of Nb₂O₅ and Ta₂O₅ (Table 2).

344

345 **4.3. U-Pb geochronology**

346 Results of U-Pb isotopic analyses of both wolframite and cassiterite samples are presented in Table 3 and
347 summarized in Fig. 5. Wolframite dating was performed on distinct hubnerites and ferberite generations
348 previously identified by their optical and compositional characteristics. For cassiterite analyses, we took
349 into account the different textures and zonings shown in CL images. Due to the presence of a high amount
350 of rutile inclusions in dissolution-recrystallization zones (i.e. especially in cassiterite from deformed veins),
351 we targeted areas interpreted as primary, non-recrystallized cassiterite.

352 In U-Pb space, analyses from both wolframite and cassiterite samples are generally discordant due to
353 variable content of non-radiogenic, initial lead. Considering the broad spread in U-Pb ratios, rather than
354 based on individual analytical spots, crystallization ages are interpreted in Tera-Wasserburg diagram (T-
355 W; ²⁰⁷Pb/²⁰⁶Pb vs. ²³⁸U/²⁰⁶Pb) as lower intercept from a regression line of all points from a single sample.

356 Wolframite gives two dates: Hub-1 wolframite yields 338.1 ± 5.8 Ma, the oldest in the studied samples,
357 and Hub-2 and Fb-2 return 322.8 ± 5.2 Ma, overprinting the earlier cassiterite formation episode. The
358 pegmatite-hosted cassiterite (MIM-Cst) is the oldest among the cassiterite samples, yielding a lower
359 intercept date of 324.1 ± 5.9 Ma. Cassiterite from quartz veins define a large spread between 320 and 300
360 Ma, having the following dates: 320.0 ± 5.8 Ma (CUB-Cst-1), 314.7 ± 5.7 Ma (RES-Cst), 310.1 ± 5.7 Ma
361 (CUB-Cst-2), 309.3 ± 3.2 Ma (VAL-Cst), 305.1 ± 6.1 Ma (CUB-Cst-3), 301.7 ± 5.4 Ma (MAT-Cst), and
362 300.7 ± 5.4 Ma (ATL-Cst).

363
364

4.4. Trace elements

365 The wolframite total rare earth element (REE) content is generally high and widely dispersed in all the
366 samples. It varies between 69 and 389 ppm in Hub-1, between 120 and 950 ppm in Hub-2 from ATL, and
367 between 16 and 122 ppm in Hub/Fb-2 from MAT. Chondrite-normalized (McDonough and Sun 1995) REE
368 concentrations of these phases have been plotted in spider diagrams. Hubnerite displays an increasing semi-
369 linear pattern for heavy rare earth elements (HREE) with a negative Eu anomaly. Contrasting the
370 concentrations of LREE (from La to Nd), MREE (from Sm to Dy) and HREE (from Ho to Lu) in this
371 sample, the ratios are $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{MREE}]_{\text{CN}}$ between 0.009 and 0.017, $[\Sigma\text{MREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$ ranging from
372 0.114 to 0.350, and $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$ between 0.002 and 0.005. In contrast, Fb-2 exhibits a flatter pattern
373 with relative depletion in medium rare earth elements (MREE). In this case, the relationship values are
374 0.933 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{MREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, 0.105 $[\Sigma\text{MREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$ and 0.082 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$.

375 Cassiterite is significantly more depleted in REE than wolframite. The CUB-Cst-3 ($\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.55\text{-}9.29$ ppm)
376 and the MIM-Cst ($\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.12\text{-}18.21$ ppm) are the more REE-enriched cassiterites. Sm, Eu, and Dy values
377 are below the limit of detection in most of the cassiterite analyses. The concentration values for Gd and Tb
378 are neither used in ΣREE calculations nor displayed in diagrams as accurate quantification of these two
379 elements with LA-ICP-MS is challenged by polyatomic interferences production during ablation and
380 aerosol transport to plasma (Yang et al., 2024), giving rise to false Gd and Tb positive anomalies in REE
381 patterns.

382 The REE diagrams lacking Gd and Tb reveal two distinct patterns. MIM-Cst, CUB-Cst-1, RES-Cst, and
383 CUB-Cst-2 cassiterites follow a relatively flat linear pattern. In the case of CUB-Cst-2 and MIM-Cst, there
384 is a LREE enrichment relative to HREE (2.71-1.73 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{MREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, 0.63-0.85 $[\Sigma\text{MREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$,
385 and 2.24-1.77 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$) while CUB-Cst-1 and RES-Cst are slightly more enriched in HREE
386 (2.72-2.14 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{MREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, 0.05-0.18 $[\Sigma\text{MREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, and 0.23-0.69 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$).

387 VAL-Cst, CUB-Cst-3, MAT-Cst, and ATL-Cst samples display a less flat pattern than the previously
388 described, with a very pronounced slope from Dy to Lu, featuring higher HREE values than the other ones.
389 They have a substantial enrichment in HREE relative to LREE (1.99-2.82 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{MREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, 0.01-0.06
390 $[\Sigma\text{MREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$, and 0.03-0.20 $[\Sigma\text{LREE}/\Sigma\text{HREE}]_{\text{CN}}$).

391 Regarding Hf-Zr composition of cassiterite, pegmatite-hosted cassiterite is the more enriched in both
392 elements (2.3 wt % Hf and 1.4 wt % Zr). Hf and Zr average contents in cassiterite from quartz veins range
393 from 0.3 to 28 ppm in Hf and from 4.6 to 301 ppm in Zr.

394

395 5. Discussion

396 5.1. Timing of the Martinamor Sn-W mineralizations in the context of the NW Iberian Massif

397 U-Pb dating of cassiterite and wolframite has revealed that the Sn-W mineralizations in the Martinamor
398 dome span over a period of 40 Myr, within which two main stages can be identified. The first stage was
399 minor and led to the formation of W-bearing veins at 338.1 ± 5.8 Ma in the dome core, within the sillimanite
400 zone, however its structural control is not well constrained (Fig. 7). The second stage comprises the main
401 mineralization period and shows a temporal and spatial correlation with extensional fabric developed across
402 the dome. It started with the formation of W-bearing veins (322.8 ± 5.2 Ma) and Sn-bearing pegmatites
403 (324.1 ± 5.9 Ma), in a similar temporal interval but occurring in well-separated sites. While W-bearing
404 veins appear in the dome core, the Sn-bearing pegmatites are found at shallower structural levels, near the
405 top of the extensional detachment, within the staurolite zone (Fig. 7). This event evolved towards formation
406 of Sn-veins from ca. 320.0 ± 5.8 Ma to 300.7 ± 5.4 Ma, resulting in a protracted period that spans over 25
407 Myr in total.

408 It is well recognized that the tectonic development of the Variscan orogeny in the Iberian Massif underwent
409 three stages of contractional deformation (C1, C2, and C3) and two extensional stages (E1 and E2), the
410 latter associated with the gravitational collapse of the orogen (Azor et al., 2019). Besides, tectonothermal
411 phases in the Variscan orogen are diachronic (e.g. Dallmeyer et al. 1997) and the orogenic front along the
412 European Variscan belt is known to show a complex geometry and evolution (Balleve et al., 2014;
413 Martínez Catalán et al. 2020). In the Iberian Massif, after major thickening phases (C1 and C2), partial
414 melting in the mid-crust, triggered a gravitational adjustment due to rheological inversion (e.g. Vanderhaeghe
415 et al., 2020). This was accommodated by syn-collisional extension structures. Early manifestations of
416 extensional structures in Iberia have been constrained around 335-330 Ma (Burg et al., 1994; Faure et al.,
417 2002; Martínez Catalán et al., 2003), and was characterized by low-dipping extensional detachments,
418 playing a significant role in crustal thinning (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014; Rubio Pascual et al., 2022) and
419 the formation of domes induced by heating events. For practical reasons, all those extensional structures
420 predating C3 phase are grouped as the first extensional phase (E1) and those postdating C3 structures, as
421 the second extensional phase (E2) (e.g. Azor et al. 2019). However, C3 compressional structures, upright
422 folds and strike-slip shear zones, developed along a wide temporal range in the Iberian Massif, between
423 325 and ca. 300 Ma (Fig. 8) (Martínez Catalán et al. 2014; Gutiérrez Alonso et al., 2015; Díez Fernández

424 and Pereira, 2017). In the Martinamor area, C3 is widespread, but appears transposed by the extensional
425 fabrics related to the Martinamor extensional dome (Díaz Balda et al. 1995). This structural argument has
426 been used to classify the Martinamor as part of the second extensional phase (E2), which has been
427 traditionally constrained to date between 315 and 308 Ma (Fig.8; Martínez Catalán et al., 2009, 2014).

428 In this context, our geochronological data have revealed some interesting facts. The first W mineralization
429 event (dated in this work at 338.1 ± 5.8 Ma; Fig. 5) is related in time to the variscan compressive phase
430 (C1) (Fig. 8) and might be representing an early, minor hydrothermal manifestation. This could be related
431 to mineralizations connected with thermal anomalies after a significant thickening event in the orogen, as
432 proposed for e.g. Sn-quartz veins in Montesinho (Portugal) with U-Pb cassiterite ages of 331.4 ± 5.6 Ma
433 (Zhang et al., 2019), or W-mineralizations developed in the French Massif Central (334.4 ± 1.7 Ma;
434 Harlaux et al., 2018).

435 The second was the main Sn-W mineralization event (dated in this study between 324.1 ± 5.9 and $300.7 \pm$
436 5.4 Ma; Fig. 5) and is related in time to the period of gravitational readjustment in the orogen (E1 and E2),
437 coeval with the C3 contractional phase, and the formation of the Central Iberian Arc (CIA, Fig. 8). We have
438 documented evidence of mineralizations that were synkinematic to late-kinematic with the extensional
439 deformation and coeval partial melting across the Martinamor dome (Fig. 8). From early mineralization
440 veins and pegmatites (324.1 ± 5.9 Ma, e.g. MIM), extensional-shear related mineralizations (314.7 ± 5.7
441 Ma, e.g. RES) to subvertical veins (300.7 ± 5.4 Ma, e.g. MAT, ATL), our results reflect a protracted
442 mineralizing activity that spanned, at least, over 25 Ma (Fig. 8).

443 In regional terms, structural arguments indicate that the Martinamor dome is an E2 extensional dome (post-
444 C3; Azor et al., 2019). However, both vein structural features and cassiterite geochronological data suggests
445 that either E2 phase initiated earlier than originally set (ca. 325 Ma) or, more likely, E1 and E2 extensional
446 phases are one and the same process. At this point it is reasonable to think that the extensional collapse
447 persisted at different structural levels across the internal zones of the Iberian Massif from 330 to 300 Ma,
448 as convergent remote stresses were active. Although the distinction between the two phases may prove
449 useful in defining the relative structural sequence in an area, it is inadvisable to apply this distinction in
450 temporal terms, given that the synconvergent gravitational readjustment, as demonstrated in our own work,
451 has a continuous character.

452 In parallel, similar cassiterite and wolframite ages (318.8 ± 5.6 to 301.0 ± 4.2 Ma) have been found in other
453 Sn-pegmatites and Sn-W vein-type deposits in Iberia, such as Ervedosa, Panasqueira, and Vieiros, in

454 Portugal (Zhang et al., 2019), and Logrosán and La Fregeneda, in Spain (Rizvanova et al., 2017; Ballouard
455 et al., 2023). They are also comparable with the age range of Sn-W mineralizations in veins, pegmatites,
456 and rare metal granites (RMG) found in the Armorican Massif and the French Massif Central (318.0 ± 5.6 -
457 303.8 ± 4.8 Ma) (Gourcerol et al., 2019; Harlaux et al., 2018, 2021, 2023; Marcoux et al., 2021; Melleton
458 et al., 2022). In some of those examples, the action of a gravitational collapse has also been suggested (e.g.
459 Harlaux et al. 2023), while in others, voluminous late- to post-tectonic magmatism prevent a detailed
460 examination of the tectonothermal context.

461 Our results suggest a W-Sn mineralization cycle spanning 40 Myr for Iberia, slightly longer than previous
462 estimations (30 Myr; Zhang et al. 2019), but similar to other sectors in the European Variscan belt (Harlaux
463 et al., 2018). This confirm a major and regionally widespread metallogenetic event connect with a large
464 scale tectonothermal event during the late-Variscan orogeny.

465

466 **5.2. Metallogenetic model.**

467 Both tin and tungsten fertile granites are typically peraluminous suites and broadly relate to partial melting
468 of metasedimentary source material (Sylvester, 1998; Lehman, 2021). Besides this common magmatic
469 affinity, different factors determine the ability of magmatic systems to form either Sn-rich or W-rich
470 deposits. The solubility of Sn in silicic melt is highly redox-dependent, and it is enhanced in reduced
471 conditions, whereas that of W is relatively insensitive to it (Che et al., 2013). Further, W strongly partitions
472 into muscovite whereas Sn partitions into both muscovite and biotite (Simons et al., 2017; Zhao et al.,
473 2022). Thus, the dehydration melting via muscovite and/or biotite breakdown will release Sn and/or W into
474 the anatectic melt (Clark et al., 2011; Zhao et al., 2022). According to Zhao et al. (2022), W-related granites
475 derive from partial melting temperatures between 700-770 °C, while Sn-related granites are generally the
476 products of higher-temperature partial melting, ranging between 760-940 °C.

477 Other factors are considered to play an important role in the formation of these deposits like subsequent
478 melt extractions during partial melting of the continental crust (Wolf et al., 2018) and the presence of an
479 enriched protolith that enhance the Sn-W metallogenetic potential of the anatectic granites (Romer et al.,
480 2014, 2016; Wolf et al., 2018). In addition, the formation of significant deposits requires the metal
481 enrichment of these granites as a consequence of fractional crystallization during their magmatic evolution
482 (Barsukov, 1957; Lehman et al., 1990, Lehman, 2021).

483 During the Variscan orogeny, in NW Iberian Massif, magmatism covers a wide temporal range from 325
484 to 285 Ma (Fig. 8). C1 and C2 contractional phases resulted in a significant crustal thickening, and thermal
485 relaxation of lower crust eventually led to partial melting, triggering syn-convergent extensional collapse
486 (E1-E2), and mass and energy redistribution across crustal levels of the orogen (Gómez Barreiro et al.,
487 2010; Alcock et al., 2015). In this context, synkinematic granites (S-type) and granodiorites intruded at ca.
488 325-305 Ma (Fig. 8; Martínez Catalán et al., 2014) and are locally associated with the formation of Sn-W
489 deposits.

490

491 **5.2.1. Source of heat and geological controls of Sn-W mineralizations.**

492 As stated earlier, the first W-mineralization event recorded in the area at 338 Ma likely represents a relic
493 of the interaction between contractional (C1) deformation and early magmatism in this sector. Considering
494 the Barrovian metamorphic assemblages in the Martinamor dome, a minimum PT conditions of ca. 5 kbar
495 and 600-700°C have been proposed in the area hosting the early W mineralization (sillimanite zone; Díez
496 Balda et al., 1995), thus providing the thermal conditions for partial melting to form W-fertile granitic melts
497 (700-770°C, Simons et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2022). Therefore, this early W-dominant hydrothermal
498 manifestation might be related to a muscovite-dehydration melting in metasediments.

499 The second mineralization stage represents a ~25 Ma protracted pulse (324-301 Ma, Fig. 8) which, within
500 the evolution framework of NW Iberia, suggests a progressive overlapping with C3 deformation, the main
501 synkinematic magmatism and the extensional collapse (Fig. 8). This fact is consistent with the first evidence
502 of migmatization in the lowermost structural levels of the footwall to the extensional detachment (332 ± 12
503 Ma; Galibert, 1984). Besides, the time range is also coeval with the formation of the Central Iberian Arc,
504 where the Martinamor dome is located in its hinge zone (Martínez Catalán et al., 2021; Durán Oreja et al.,
505 2023). Our data further reveal that the mineralization expands through the extensional collapse phase,
506 during which the Martinamor gneissic dome formed (Fig. 8). Also, the presence of Sn mineralizations since
507 the very start of this stage suggest that partial melting may have reached biotite-dehydration conditions at
508 depth. These observations point to a persistent source of heat throughout this period to trigger and sustain
509 mineralization events over a protracted interval (~25 Myr).

510 Regarding this necessary heat, two different large-scale mechanisms can be invoked here (i.e.: Castro, 2014;
511 Vanderhaeghe et al., 2020; Romer and Kroner, 2016) a) the emplacement of high/ultra-high temperature
512 metamorphic rocks thrust during continental collision, or b) the emplacement of mantle-derived melts.

513 Usually, the first explanation has been invoked for many of the European Variscan Sn-W deposits
514 (Vanderhaeghe et al., 2020; Romer and Kroner, 2016). In the Iberian Massif the emplacement of the
515 allocthonous nappe occurred about 340 Ma, but its thickness and geometry was probably highly
516 heterogeneous (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014, 2020, 2021) casting doubts on its role in heat advection in
517 the orogen. In addition, partial melting driven by barrovian metamorphism in this zone is likely not the
518 heat-providing mechanism, since metamorphic gradient in this zone was not enough to produce in situ
519 biotite-dehydration melting. Furthermore, the absence of tangential deformation (C2) and significant crustal
520 thickening in the area (5 kbar; Díez Balda et al., 1995), requires an additional source of heat to the system
521 to trigger rheological inversion and extensional collapse (e.g. Rey et al. 2001).

522 Interestingly, the onset of this mineralizing stage coincides with the formation of the CIA orocline at 325
523 Ma (Duran Oreja et al. 2023). Considering the large amount of mineralization and magmatism observed,
524 not only in the region studied, but on a regional scale in this time period, it is plausible that the heat
525 necessary to activate those phenomena has its origin in processes of mantle advection and magmatic
526 underplating, as already proposed in different sections of the variscan lithosphere in Europe (e.g. Schuster
527 and Stüwe, 2008; Petri et al., 2017). This would provide the necessary conditions not only to reach biotite-
528 breakdown melting conditions of metapelitic protoliths, generating Sn-W specific magmas, but also for the
529 rheological weakening of the orogenic pile (Rey et al. 2001; Foley, 2008). The heat advection may have
530 been initiated or favored by large scale processes like the CIA orocline formation at 325 Ma (Durán Oreja
531 et al., 2023) through lithospheric delamination at its hinge zone, where most magmatism and significant
532 gneissic domes are located (Schulmann et al., 2022).

533 In the Figure 9a we summarize a metallogenetic model for the formation of Sn-W mineralizations in the
534 Martinamor dome. Some W-bearing veins probably developed during compressional phases (C1 to C3), at
535 338 Ma representing a small hydrothermal event anticipating the progressive development of a thermal
536 anomaly at depth, first due to thermal relaxation after tectonic thickening, and second related to large scale
537 folding (C3 + CIA orocline) and heat advection driven by delamination. Sn-bearing pegmatites and Sn-W-
538 bearing veins formed during the onset of gravitational readjustments originated by the thermal anomaly
539 associated to CIA driven delamination. Afterwards, widespread extensional deformation dominates (315-
540 300 Ma), and footwall unroofing through the extensional detachment provided a favorable environment for
541 multiple and progressive Sn-vein formation through the shear zone and consistent with extensional flow at
542 different scales (Fig. 3b). Partial melting is widespread in lower structural levels, forming a diffuse network

543 of granitic leucosomes, in general, concordant with the foliation and deformed, or locally subconcordant
544 due to melt migration to dilatant sites (e.g. Vanderhaeghe et al., 2020).

545 Understanding the spatial and temporal distribution of the mineralization requires to explore the potential
546 role of the extensional detachment for channeling mineralized fluids. Extensional detachments develop
547 steep thermal gradients (Álvarez Valero et al., 2014), so that rheological changes are expected to occur
548 around them, favouring the creation of dilatant traps. This may happen due to a progressive exhumation of
549 the dome core (doming effect) eventually reaching the brittle-ductile transition (Fig. 9b). This change could
550 explain why Sn-veins developed in increasingly deeper zones over time, in a more structurally suitable
551 environment for the generation of these mineralizations. However other mechanisms could be operating
552 like the combination of fluids overpressure and lithologies of contrasted viscosity, to create dilatant sites
553 for ore precipitation.

554

555 The precipitation of cassiterite from magmatic hydrothermal fluids in Sn deposits takes place between 300
556 and 500°C (Little, 1960; Naumov et al., 2011; Bodnar et al., 2014) regardless of the precipitation process
557 that led to the mineralization. These temperatures are compatible with deformation conditions across the
558 extensional shear zone (Díez Balda et al., 1995; Gómez Barreiro et al., 2024), so that transport of Sn-rich
559 hydrothermal fluids through the extensional detachment could be possible during isothermal exhumation
560 and subsequent cooling covering the entire activity of the extensional detachment (Díez Balda et al., 1995).

561 As suggested by their structural control (Fig. 3), those mineralizations developed in a ductile-brittle
562 deformation regime. Since cassiterite can precipitate once host-rocks reaches temperatures < 500°C,
563 assuming that the exsolved fluid from the granites will cool down on its way up through the extensional
564 detachment, the mineralization window for vein cassiterite deposition could be tentatively controlled by
565 the ductile-brittle transition, leading to the development of suitable structures for mineral deposition.

566 Assuming a granitic composition and natural strain rates ($10^{-14}\cdot s^{-1}$), the transition temperature has been
567 established at $400 \pm 100^\circ C$ (Goetze et al., 1979; Kohlstedt et al., 1995; Violay et al., 2017). Regarding the
568 tectono-metamorphic evolution depicted by Díez Balda et al., (1995), the mineralizing window for
569 cassiterite-bearing veins will reach progressively deeper structural levels with time during the exhumation
570 (Fig. 9b-1 and 2). Furthermore, youngest veins from Matamala ad Atalaya (302-301 Ma) occur crosscutting
571 the orthogneisses in a brittle-ductile deformation regime, without signs of later ductile post-depositional
572 deformation. This suggests that at this point in the thermal evolution of the terrane the temperature

573 conditions in the dome core might have been below 450°C, matching with the last retrometamorphic stage
574 interpreted as a latekinematic cooling (Fig. 9b-3).

575

576 **5.2.2. Wolframite and cassiterite compositional variation through time.**

577 The wolframite and cassiterite REE contents also reflect an evolution of the mineralizing system with time.
578 W-bearing veins characterize the first, minor mineralization event at 338 Ma, and are also present at the
579 onset of the second, main mineralization event, at 323 Ma (Fig. 8). A comparison of average wolframite
580 REE composition from the two mineralization events is found in Figure 10. In both cases, hubnerite show
581 a quite similar REE pattern with a slight fractionation from HREE to LREE and a moderate negative Eu
582 anomaly. In contrast, ferberite from the second mineralization event shows a similar pattern from Lu to Gd
583 for HREE and MREE, albeit with a lower content, lacks Eu anomaly, and shows an enrichment towards
584 LREE from Sm to La.

585 Hubnerites from the first and second mineralization events have very similar major and trace element
586 composition (Table 2, Fig. 10) despite being crystallized at different temporal intervals. This could imply
587 that they formed under similar metallogenic conditions, although they developed during slightly different
588 tectonic regimes; the first one (338 Ma) formed during a main crustal thickening regime and the second
589 one (323 Ma) developed at the start of the syn-collisional extension.

590 Regarding the hubnerite and ferberite from the second event, they display overlapping crystallization ages,
591 although the former is being replaced by the latter. This indicate that the ferberite should be slightly
592 younger, albeit separated by a temporal interval below the resolution of the applied methodology (i.e. a few
593 Myrs). This change in major element composition of wolframite suggests a step decrease of the Mn/Fe
594 ratio, likely resulting from addition of Fe through fluid-rock interactions (Michaud and Pichavant, 2019).
595 This pattern has been documented in other Variscan W deposits like Argemela and Vale das Gatas in
596 Portugal (Lecumberri-Sanchez et al., 2017; Neiva, 2008).

597 Trace element data in cassiterite highlight the existence of two compositional groups, with average Σ REE
598 contents over 1 ppm and up to 0.6 ppm, respectively. The most enriched in REE are the cassiterite grown
599 in Sn-bearing pegmatites at 324 Ma (av. Σ REE = 1.02 ppm [MIM-Cst]) and the cassiterite from quartz
600 veins CUB-Cst-3 at 305 Ma (av. Σ REE = 3.50 ppm [CUB-Cst-3]). It is noteworthy that cassiterites from
601 309 Ma onwards record a marked increase in HREE (Fig. 10) resulting a tendency to become progressively
602 richer in Σ REE with time: CUB-Cst-1, av. Σ REE = 0.04 ppm; RES-Cst, av. Σ REE = 0.05 ppm; CUB-Cst-

603 2, av. $\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.10$ ppm; VAL-Cst, av. $\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.57$ ppm; MAT-Cst, av. $\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.24$ ppm; ATL-Cst, av.
604 $\Sigma\text{REE} = 0.42$ ppm.

605 Zr and Hf in cassiterite (Fig. 11) show an interesting variation with time. Concentrations of, Zr_{CN} and Hf_{CN}
606 show a consistent depletion from older to younger cassiterites between 324 to 305 Ma (mean Hf_{CN} from
607 2.2 wt% to 2.6 ppm, and Zr_{CN} from 0.3 wt% to 1.2 ppm), and also in $(\text{Hf}/\text{Zr})_{\text{CN}}$ average values (from 5.7 to
608 0.9) (Fig. 11a). In contrast, between 305 to 301 Ma the opposite trend can be observed, i.e. an increase in
609 Hf_{CN} (from 2.6 to 62 ppm), in Zr_{CN} (from 1.2 to 37 ppm), and in $(\text{Hf}/\text{Zr})_{\text{CN}}$ average values (from 0.9 to 1.7)
610 (Fig. 11b).

611 These trends in Hf-Zr cassiterite composition fit with the tectonometamorphic evolution of the dome and
612 the proposed metallogenic model and they might be reflecting protracted changes in the Sn-W mineral
613 system during its ~25 Myr lifespan. Further research is needed to understand the origin of these trends;
614 however, some future tentative working hypothesis can be suggested at a glance. The main trend depicts a
615 decreasing Hf vs Zr trend for a ~19 My span which could be related with changes in the composition of the
616 Sn-W melts through time, either while their ascent and crystallization (i.e. crystallization of Zr and Hf
617 bearing phases) or due to an increasing input of mantle melts (i.e. dilution of Zr and Hf content) during the
618 gravitational collapse. Regarding the reverse trend in the last 4 My (305-301 Ma), it is probably correlated
619 with the increase in HREE in cassiterite at 309 Ma (Fig. 10). We tentatively propose that these chemical
620 changes could be related to a shift in the Martinamor dome tectono-thermal evolution from an isothermal
621 decompression during its exhumation, to a last stage of post kinematic retrograde metamorphism with a
622 temperature decrease.

623

624 **6. Conclusions**

625 We have documented a 40Myr timespan of Sn-W mineralizations in the Martinamor dome in the Variscan
626 Iberian Massif (Spain) by LA-ICP-MS U-Pb dating of cassiterite and wolframite. Mineralization has been
627 correlated with the tectonothermal evolution recorded in the area and its regional implications, discussed.

628

629 The first, and probably minor, event generated W-dominant hydrothermal ores at 338.1 ± 5.8 Ma (U-Pb /
630 Wolframite). There is no structural information of these veins, but the age could be associated with the
631 compressional phase C1, and potentially linked to muscovite dehydration melting during Barrovian
632 prograde metamorphism associated with tectonic thickening during this Variscan stage.

633

634 The second event is the principal Sn-W mineralization phase, and has been constrained by wolframite and
635 cassiterite U-Pb dating from 324.1 ± 5.9 Ma to 300.7 ± 5.4 Ma. Mineralized veins have been consistently
636 correlated with the extensional deformation flow which accommodated gravitational collapse of the
637 Variscan orogen, and eventually formed the Martinamor gneissic dome. Our results demonstrate that the
638 extensional collapse is a continuous phenomenon, and the use of E1 and E2 denominations has to be
639 restricted to structural sequencing without age implications.

640

641 The spatial and temporal distribution of the Sn-W vein deposits in the district is related to the rheological
642 changes associated to the extensional shearing and the progressive exhumation of the dome core, which
643 favored the creation of dilatant sites for ore precipitation. The Hf, Zr and REE cassiterite compositional
644 variations through time reflect changes in the Sn-W mineral system consistent with the tectonothermal
645 evolution of the dome.

646

647 It is proposed that the partial melting of metasedimentary protoliths originated Sn- and W-enriched granitic
648 melts, through biotite-dehydration melting ($760-940^{\circ}\text{C}$) and muscovite-dehydration melting ($700-770^{\circ}\text{C}$)
649 respectively. To reach those conditions more heat is required to add to the metamorphic thermal conditions
650 documented during C1. As the main Sn-W coincided with the formation of the Central Iberian Arc (CIA)
651 and widespread magmatism, we suggest that thermal advection, likely induced by lithospheric delamination
652 during CIA formation, provided the heat required to reach melting conditions and generate Sn-W-rich
653 magmas over this protracted period of 25 Myr. Besides, this process led to the mechanical weakening of
654 the crust which resulted in the gravitational collapse of the Variscan orogen.

655

656 The chronology of the Sn-W mineralizations at Martinamor (338-301 Ma) aligns with other metallogenic
657 events in the Variscan Belt. It highlights the importance of integrate ore geology within tectonothermal
658 investigations to better understand not only the orogenic evolution, but also generate consistent exploration
659 strategies, upscaling district to regional mineral system models.

660

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663

664 **Declaration of competing interest**

665 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
666 could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

667

668 **Acknowledgements**

669 This work was supported by the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 under the grants PID2020-
670 117332GB-C22 and PID2020-117332GB-C21; the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and European
671 Union Next Generation EU/PRTR under the grant TED2021-130440B-I00.

672 The author Daniel Bermejo expresses his gratitude for the funding provided by the Universidad
673 Complutense de Madrid and Banco Santander through a predoctoral contract (CT82/20-CT83/20).

674 The LA-ICP-MS analytical facility has been partially supported by an ETH Zürich Career Seed Award to
675 Lorenzo Tavazzani.

676 Kelvin dos Santos Alves thanks the funding received from the Universidad de Salamanca and Banco
677 Santander through a predoctoral contract from the 2022 call.

678

679 **Data Availability**

680 The dataset used for this research is available in the supplementary material.

681

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1075 **Table and figure captions:**

1076 **Table 1.** General description of the studied mineralizations in Martinamor.

1077 **Table 2.** Average chemical composition of the studied ore minerals in Martinamor. *Analyzed only with LA-ICP-SF-
1078 MS.

1079 **Table 3.** U-Pb ages of the studied mineralizations in Martinamor.

1080 **Fig. 1.** Zones of the Variscan Iberian Massif. The locations of the principal gneissic domes are indicated in red. The
1081 location of the Martinamor gneissic dome is indicated (Fig. 2). Modified after Martínez Catalán et al. (2014).

1082 **Fig. 2.** Geological map and cross-section of the Martinamor Gneiss dome. In inset position of the Martinamor dome
1083 in the Iberian Massif. Black dashed lines in the cross-section represent S_{E2} extensional foliation. Abbreviations: CZ;
1084 Cantabrian Zone. WALZ; West Asturian-Leonese Zone. GTMZ; Galicia-Tras-Os-Montes Zone. CIZ; Central Iberian
1085 Zone. OMZ; Ossa-morena Zone. SPZ; South Portuguese Zone. Modified after Díez Balda et al. (1995) and Martínez
1086 Catalán et al. (2019).

1087 **Fig. 3.** Structural features of mineralized Sn-W veins from Martinamor. **a)** deformed and boudinaged Sn-bearing
1088 pegmatite lying parallel to the S_{E2} foliation (Mimosa; MIM) **b)** boudinage-neck Qtz+Tur+Cst style mineralizations
1089 related to the $E2$ extensional phase (Rescatada; RES) **c)** deformed and boudinaged Qtz+Tur+Cst veins oriented sub-
1090 parallel to the S_{E2} (Rescatada; RES) **d)** Subvertical Qtz+Cst veins crosscutting the metasedimentary sequence (Atalaya;
1091 ATL).

1092 **Fig. 4. a)** Isoriented centimeter-sized tabular crystals of Hub-1. **b)** Aggregate of small crystals of Hub-2 and Fb-2. **c)** Fb-
1093 2 replaces a Hub-2 crystal. (Reflected light, PPL). **d)** Cassiterite crystals from the Sn-pegmatite (MIM). **e)** Dissolved and
1094 fractured crystals of cassiterite from the pegmatite (RL, PPL). **f)** Cathodoluminescence (CL) image of cassiterite from
1095 the pegmatite. **g)** Cassiterite crystals from vein swarm (CUB). **h)** Dissolved and highly fractured cassiterite (CUB). **i)** CL
1096 image of different cassiterites from vein swarm (CUB). **j)** Cassiterites from deformed Qtz-Tur veins (RES). **k)** Dissolved
1097 and fractured cassiterite from deformed Qtz-Tur veins with rutile in dissolved zones (RL, PPL) (RES). **l)** CL image of
1098 cassiterites from deformed Qtz-Tur veins (RES and VAL). **m)** Cassiterites from non-deformed subvertical quartz veins
1099 (ATL). **n)** Slightly fractured cassiterite from non-deformed subvertical veins (MAT). **o)** CL image of cassiterite from
1100 non-deformed subvertical veins. (ATL).

1101 **Fig. 5.** Tera-Wasserburg U-Pb diagrams for analyzed wolframite and cassiterite samples. Isochrones are unanchored
1102 and reported lower intercept ages include excess variance (1.8% for cassiterite; Carr et al., 2023; 2.0% for wolframite;
1103 Carr et al., 2021).

1104 **Fig. 6. a-b)** Chondrite-normalized REE plots of Hub-1 (purple), Hub-2 (dark blue) and Fb-2 (light blue). **c-d)** Chondrite-
1105 normalized REE plots of cassiterite. Cst from pegmatite (MIM-Cst) is represented in black color, while cassiterites
1106 from veins are represented in a brown to green color ramp, from oldest to youngest respectively (CUB-Cst-1/RES-
1107 Cst/CUB-Cst-2/VAL-Cst/CUB-Cst-3/MAT-Cst/ATL-Cst) with the same color scheme used in Fig. 5.

1108 **Fig. 7.** Cross section of the Martinamor dome including ages of wolframite and cassiterite in pegmatite and vein-type
1109 mineralizations.

1110 **Figure 8.** Summary of the geochronology of Martinamor Sn-W vein-type and pegmatite mineralizations and their
1111 tectonothermal context. Chronology of the principal Variscan tectonic phases (C: contractional; E: extensional
1112 collapse), related magmatism and development of oroclines: Central Iberian Arc (CIA) and Ibero-Armorican Arc
1113 (IAA). Traditional temporal boundaries for E1 and E2 are showed (Azor et al., 2019). Based on Dallmeyer et al. (1997),
1114 Martínez Catalán et al. (2014), Alcock et al. (2015), Ribeiro et al. (2019); Azor et al. (2019) and Duran Oreja et al.
1115 (2023).

1116 **Fig. 9. a)** Metallogenetic model for Sn-W mineralizations in the Martinamor gneissic dome. During compressional
1117 phases (C1-C3) thermal relaxation due to tectonic thickening, and heat advection probably driven by CIA orocline
1118 formation, led to the formation of the initial mineralizations; The onset of the gravitational collapse initiates at ca.
1119 324Ma, supported by the correlation of mineralized structures and extensional flow. Later on extensional collapse
1120 dominates in the area, overwriting C3 structures in the Martinamor dome, so that it is represented as E2. Multiple Sn-
1121 deposits were formed synkinematically with the extensional shear zone in the 315-300 Ma late period **b)** Location of
1122 the structurally most suitable zones for cassiterite mineralization through the late evolution of the extensional
1123 detachment. Cassiterite mineralization window is based on the ductile-brittle transition temperature range ($400 \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$;
1124 Violay et al., 2017) and the temperature interval for cassiterite formation (e.g. Little, 1960; Naumov et al., 2011; Bodnar
1125 et al., 2014).

1126 **Fig. 10.** Average chondrite-normalized (McDonough and Sun, 1995) REE patterns of studied wolframite and
1127 cassiterite. In cassiterite, when most of the measured spots for Sm, Eu and Dy fall below the detection limit, the BLD
1128 value has been assumed as zero for the average calculation, so these values are represented with dotted lines.

1129 **Fig. 11.** Chondrite normalized concentrations (McDonough and Sun, 1995) of Zr and Hf in cassiterites of the main
1130 mineralization event. **a)** Zr_{CN} vs. Hf_{CN} plot showing a progressive depletion from 324 to 305 Ma **b)** Zr_{CN} vs. Hf_{CN} plot
1131 showing an enrichment trend from 305 to 301 Ma.

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1139 Table 1

Mineral		Sample name	Mine	Mineralization style	Mineral association	Related alteration
Wolframite	Hubnerite	Hub-1	Matamala	Veins	Hub	Unknown
		Hub-2	Matamala-Atalaya		Hub	Unknown
	Ferberite	Fb-2	Matamala		Hub + Fb	Unknown
Cassiterite	MIM-Cst	Mimosa	Deformed Sn-pegmatite	Cst + Ap + Fd + Qtz + Ms + Bt	None	
	CUB-Cst-1	El Cubito	Vein swarms	Cst + Tur	Tourmalinization ± greisen	
	CUB-Cst-2			Cst + Tur	Tourmalinization ± greisen	
	CUB-Cst-3			Cst + Sulfides	Unknown	
	RES-Cst	La Rescatada	Boudinage-related and deformed subhorizontal veins	Cst + Tur	Tourmalinization ± greisen	
	VAL-Cst	Valle Largo		Cst + Tur	Tourmalinization ± greisen	
	ATL-Cst	Atalaya	Subvertical veins	Cst + Ms	Greisen	
	MAT-Cst	Matamala		Cst + Ms	Greisen	

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1156 Table 2

Mineral		Sample name	Number of analyzed crystals	Major element composition (average wt.%, EPMA)				
				WO ₃	FeO	MnO	Nb ₂ O ₅ + Ta ₂ O ₅	n
Wolframite	Hubnerite	Hub-1	1	76.19	4.20	19.29	0.35	17
		Hub-2	4	76.04	9.49	13.98	0.48	36
	Ferberite	Fb-2	2	76.10	17.67	6.28	B.D.L	15
				SnO ₂	TiO ₂	FeO+MnO	Nb ₂ O ₅ + Ta ₂ O ₅	n
Cassiterite		MIM-Cst	4	98.17	0.05	0.30	1.53	30
		CUB-Cst-1	2	97.49	0.88	0.25	1.60	15
		CUB-Cst-2	7	99.12	0.50	0.10	0.57	37
		CUB-Cst-3*	2	~ 94	-	6.11	0.06	12
		RES-Cst	10	99.30	0.43	0.05	0.13	27
		VAL-Cst	11	99.44	0.41	0.05	0.16	17
		ATL-Cst	6	99.15	0.33	0.08	0.16	32
		MAT-Cst	6	99.00	0.30	0.10	0.16	21

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1175 Table 3

Mineral	Sample name	Number of analyzed crystals	Dates (LA-ICP-SF-MS)								
			Lower Intercept Age (Ma)	Uncertainty ($\pm 2\sigma$, Ma)	Uncertainty with Ssys ($\pm 2\sigma$, Ma)	Pb c	Uncertainty Pb c ($\pm 2\sigma$)	MSWD	n	Outliers removed	
Wolfra	Hubnerite	Hub-1	1	338.1	2.8	5.8	0.930	0.140	1.20	19	1
		Hub-2	4	322.8	2.0	5.2	0.903	0.000	1.20	42	3
	Ferberite	Fb-2	2								
Cassiterite	MIM-Cst	4	324.1	0.5	5.9	0.634	0.013	1.00	56	9	
	CUB-Cst-1	2	320.0	0.6	5.8	0.690	0.014	1.10	32	0	
	CUB-Cst-2	7	310.1	0.8	5.6	0.901	0.012	1.30	47	0	
	CUB-Cst-3*	2	305.1	2.8	6.1	0.921	0.005	0.56	12	0	
	RES-Cst	10	314.7	0.6	5.7	0.877	0.003	1.50	86	0	
	VAL-Cst	11	309.3	0.6	3.2	0.856	0.002	1.60	57	0	
	ATL-Cst	6	300.7	0.3	5.4	0.929	0.024	1.20	121	0	
	MAT-Cst	6	301.7	0.4	5.4	0.878	0.022	0.94	88	0	

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1298 **Figure 10**

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1313 Figure 11

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